

A REVIEW AND ANALYSIS OF REDUCED FRP BONDED BARS IN REINFORCED CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

The American Concrete Institute (ACI) 440.1R-15 Guide for the Design and Construction of Structural Concrete Reinforced with Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Bars linearly reduces the bar stress and thereby pull-out capacity of GFRP bars to zero from an embedment length at 20 bar diameters (d_b) or less. Most experimental research and data examine the development length of various FRP bars at longer, more traditional, embedment lengths. A database was created from select available data in literature to compare to empirical standards. This investigation examines the bond performance of short embedded FRP bars into concrete considering a pull-out failure mode to expand the understanding of short embedded FRP bars into concrete.

KEYWORDS

Bond performance; Bond strength; Embedment length; Pull-out test; Rebar diameter; Rebar type.

INTRODUCTION

The advantages of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) bars as a replacement to more traditional mild steel bars used in reinforced concrete (RC) construction has been widely documented over the past two to three decades. FRP materials have a number of advantages, but the most important attribute among these is its non-corrosive nature. Whether the FRP bar is composed of glass, basalt, or carbon fibres in combination with a resin system, these products are an excellent non-metallic reinforcing option to combat the potential for corrosion in RC. Since the 1990's the design standards have continued to mature just as the fibre-resin matrix systems have also improved leading to product improvements. As FRP products are implemented more and more in the field, particularly in rehabilitation projects, there are more and more applications where the embedment length in concrete is reduced leading to questions about bar pull-out capacity. In these field applications, the case of developing continuity between concrete elements arises where the available distance to embed bars into concrete restricts the embedment lengths to short distances, in some cases 6 inches or less. Sometimes this relates to new construction and other times to rehabilitation or repair.

The ACI 440.1R-15 *Guide for the Design and Construction of Structural Concrete Reinforced with Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Bars* linearly reduces the bond capacity of FRP bars to zero from an embedment length at $20d_b$. In this study, the author has undertaken an effort to collect data from available literature. While most experimental research and data examine the development length of various FRP bars at longer, more traditional, embedment lengths. This investigation examines the bond performance of short embedded FRP bars into concrete to expand the understanding of short embedded FRP bars into concrete given the wide variety of FRP manufactured bars. Data specifically from pull-out testing with bonded embedment lengths less than 20 bar diameters (d_b) was targeted for formation of the database in this investigation. The results are compared to the current ACI 440.1R development length expression with embedment lengths less than $20d_b$.

LITERATURE REVIEW HIGHLIGHTS

Bond Test Methods and Contributing Factors for Bond

The bond between FRP rebars and concrete has been studied by many authors using different test methods. Before presenting the details of the database, the following section presents some highlights of various studies using a pull-out test of FRP bars in concrete to assess bond behaviour. There are actually several testing approaches to understanding bond behaviour of bars to concrete including not only the pull-out test, but also the beam splice test, the beam anchorage test, and the beam end test.

These four tests are shown in Fig. 1. The literature review selected previous reported publications of selective FRP bond tests over the past two decades that involve different type FRP bars, different size bars, different embedment lengths, different strength and types of concrete including sustainable concretes as well as higher strength concretes. Bond is affected by many factors including the surface roughness of the FRP bar, which is affected by the bar finish (deformed or smooth, or any surface treatment done on the bar), the mechanical interlock of the FRP bars against the concrete that may or may not exist, the chemical adhesion of the bar, the concrete strength, the type of reinforcing bar, the elastic modulus of the bar, the placement of the FRP bar and cover in the concrete, the hydrostatic pressure against the FRP bar due to shrinkage of hardened concrete, and swelling of the FRP rebars due to temperature change and moisture absorption.

Figure 1. Common bond testing methods [adapted from Alghazali and Myers (2017)]

Bond properties influence the splice lengths, concrete cover, and development length. Unlike mild steel used in RC that is a homogeneous material, FRP bars are linear-elastic and properties vary across axis depending on the orientation of the fibre. FRP bar manufacturers also produce bars with varied fibre-resin volume fractions, in different sizes, with different fibres, and use different surface treatments & deformations, therefore the properties of the bars vary greatly from producer to producer (unlike mild steel bars that are standardized) and therefore the bond performance varies. This certainly complicates the variability in bond behaviour compared to a more standardized reinforcing material such as mild steel.

Direct Tension Test Failure Modes

In terms of a direct tension test like the pull-out test, there is more than one failure mode that may occur depending on the details of the reinforcing material, specimen geometry such as clear cover, and embedded length of the rebar. Common modes of failure include a splitting failure of the concrete, a concrete failure cone pull-out with the bar intact, or pull-out of the bar itself from the concrete as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. FRP pull-out specimen and bond mechanism [adapted from Al-Khafaji et al. (2022a)]

Since most FRP bars are manufactured without deformation patterns or lugs like mild steel bars that provide added bearing resistance, pull-out of the FRP bar from the concrete (i.e.,

stripping failure) occurs more commonly in the direct pull-out test. In some field cases, FRP bars may also be doweled and epoxy anchored into existing concrete which can lead to another type failure mode that could be failure in the epoxy leading to pull-out of the bar from the epoxy or bar/adhesive from the concrete interface.

Case Study on Influence of Bond Failure Modes

In this discussion a case study analysis is investigated to explore the possible failure modes in a GFRP pull-out analysis for short embedment lengths with adequate cover. The typical failure modes that may result include a concrete cone breakout failure, a bar pull-out “stripping” failure (see Fig. 2), a bar tension failure (rupture), or a bond/adhesive failure if the bar is epoxy doweled into the concrete. In this analysis, the following was selected for comparison: 5000 psi compressive strength concrete, a #5 GFRP commercially available bar with tensile strength of 105 ksi, modulus of elasticity of 7320 ksi, and an epoxy shear capacity to concrete of 1150 psi. The results are shown in Fig. 3. In this case, a concrete pull-out failure or bar stripping failure from the concrete is much more likely than rupture of the bar. In an epoxy dowel condition with the aforementioned properties, a bond/adhesive failure is most likely. Using experimental results from Al-Khafaji et al. (2021) in similar concrete strength, one may also observe that a bond failure of the bar from the concrete may occur depending on the parameters of the bar, concrete properties, and embedment length.

Figure 3. GFRP Direct Tension Pull-out Failure Modes

FORMATION OF THE DATABASE

In the effort to collect data from literature, there were several constraints adhered to. They included collecting data from a single type of bond test, namely the common rebar concrete pull-out prism test. This was selected because much of this test data includes tests that have a short embedment length less than $20d_b$. Test results from those that are less than $20d_b$, in the region where ACI 440.1R implements a linear reduction in maximum developable bond strength, was also imposed. All of the bond test data fell within this bonded length criteria generally in the range from $5d_b$ to $15d_b$. RILEM recommends a minimum $5d_b$ bonded length to properly evaluate the bond behaviour. Fig. 4. shows a schematic of a typical FRP pull-out test specimen, while Fig. 5 shows a typical testing set-up used by many of the researchers from which the literature was collected. There was no restriction on the fibre reinforcing type of the bar; therefore, the data included test results from basalt, glass, and carbon FRP bars. However, with that being said, much of the test results (over 90%) were that of GFRP and BFRP. The bar size within the studies collected also generally all varied from as small as #3 to as large as #6 nominal bar sizes in the case of glass or basalt bars. There was also no restriction of the type of concrete or compressive strength of the concrete. Much of the tests were conducted in conventional concrete within an everyday concrete usage strength range of 4000 to 6000 psi at test age. However, some tests were conducted in higher strength concrete or utilized more exotic concretes such as fibre-reinforced concrete (FRC), ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) or highly sustainable concretes such as high-volume fly ash concrete (HVFA) that may influence the bond

behaviour of the bar to the concrete. It was understood that using a larger bandwidth of variables would result in an overall higher level of scatter within the test results collected; however, the intent of the study was to understand at a higher level how more recent short embedment data relates to the ACI 440.1R code expression for the stress in the bar developed.

Figure 4. Schematic of FRP pull-out specimen and mechanism from concrete prism [adapted from Al-Khafaji, Myers, Alghazali (2021)]

Figure 5. Pull-out test set-up [adapted from Lu et al. (2021)]

DESCRIPTION OF DATABASE STUDIES

The details of the database included a total of 13 studies. While the collection of articles in literature certainly does not incorporate all of the bond related studies that have been undertaken over the past two to three decades on the topic of FRP bars, it was intended to collect a reasonable number of data points to examine the general behaviour of reduced embedded bonded rebars. The following highlights the articles collected to assemble this particular database. In 1998, Tighiouart et al. evaluated four nominal diameters of FRP (and steel rebars), and three embedment lengths, of 6, 10 and 16 times the rebar diameter were used. Moreover, three embedment lengths depths were investigated in the 18 pullout specimens. Katz et al. (1999) studied four types of FRP bars (and steel rebars), all one nominal size with varied surface textures, three different resin systems, one mix design with one embedment length of 5 times the rebar diameter. For the purposes of this data base, only the tests at room temperature were included. Baena et al. (2009) evaluated eighty-eight concrete pull-out test which included two different FRP bar types (and steel rebars), four bar sizes, four different surface treatments, four different resin systems, two different mix designs with one embedment length of 5 times the rebar diameter. El Refai et al. (2014) evaluated forty-eight (36 BFRP, 12 GFRP) concrete pull-out test which included the two different FRP bar types, three bar sizes, two separate surface treatments that included different resin systems with one mix design and embedment lengths of 5, 7, 10, and 15 times the rebar diameter.

In addition, Lu et al. (2021) examined the bond of BFRP bars in two concretes (with and without fly ash) and one embedment length of 7 times the rebar diameter. Only the control specimens were used as part of the database in this study and not the test results for the immersed bars that were

part of the durability study in the research project. Wang et al. (2021) examined the effect of recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) on bond of BFRP bars by conducting 32 pull-out bond tests in total. Their variables included three nominal diameter size of BFRP (and steel rebar), three concrete strengths, cover thickness, four embedment length, five recycled aggregate content levels, and four embedment lengths per bar size ranging from 4.17 to 12.5 times the rebar diameter in RAC. Yoo et al. (2015) evaluated one nominal diameter size of FRP (and steel rebar), three embedment lengths of 1, 1.5, 2, 3 and 4 times the rebar diameter in ultra-high performance fibre reinforced concrete (UHPFRC). These very short embedment lengths were selected rather than the RILEM recommendation of $5d_b$ in this study because of the ultra-high strength fibre reinforced nature of the concrete to prevent rebar rupture before a pull-out failure to better investigate the embedment length on the bond properties. Hassan et al. (2016) conducted 50 pull-out tests in conventional concrete (CC) which included BFRP bars with an embedment length of 5 times the rebar diameter. Most of the tests involved environmental exposure and only control specimen data is included in this dataset. Hussain et al. (2022) conducted 36 pull-out tests in high strength concrete (HSC) which included BFRP, using three bar sizes, with three different embedment lengths of 5, 10 and 15 times the rebar diameter. Only the control specimens were used as part of the database in this study and not the bars and samples immersed in alkaline solution or seawater. Al-Khafaji et al. (2021) tested 21 pull-out specimens composed of two different GFRP bar sizes, namely #4 and #6 (and steel rebar) in three concrete types including highly sustainable concrete. Al-Khafaji et al. (2022a,b) further studied the pull-out behaviour of two different GFRP bar sizes (and steel rebar) in three concrete types including conventional concrete as well as 50% and 70% fly ash replacement of cement. A bonded embedment length meeting $5d_b$ was investigated. Subhani et al. (2023) evaluated concrete pull-out for BFRP, GFRP, & CFRP bar types (and steel rebars), that included two separate surface treatments in one mix design, with two different embedment lengths of 5, and $10d_b$ [for 6 mm (#4) bar] and 8, and $10d_b$ [for 10 mm (#5) bar].

Table 1: Summary of variables in data collected

Data Source	Bar Type (B–C–G)	Bar Size ¹ d_{dia} (mm)	Bonded Length, d_b	Special Concrete	Temp. / Durability	Microstructure Investigation
Tighiouart et al. (1998)	G	13, 16, 19, 25	6, 10, 16	CC		
Katz et al. (1999)	G	13	5	CC	X	
Baena et al. (2009)	C, G	10, 12, 16 (C) 7, 9, 12, 14, 16, 17, 19, 21 (G)	5	CC		
El Refai et al. (2014)	B, G	8, 10, 12 (B) 5, 7, 10, 15 (G)	5, 7, 10, 15	CC		
Lu et al. (2021)	B	12	7	FAC		X
Wang et al. (2021)	B	10, 12, 16	4.2 to 12.5	RAV		
Yoo et al. (2015)	G	13, 16	1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4	UHPFRC		
Hassan et al. (2016)	B	12	5	CC	X	X
Hussain et al. (2022)	B	13, 16, 19	5, 10, 15	HSC	X	X
Al-Khafaji et al. (2021)	G	13, 19	5	HVFAC		
Al-Khafaji et al. (2022a)	G	13, 19	5	EC		X
Al-Khafaji et al. (2022b)	G	13, 19	5	EC		
Subhani et al. (2023)	B, G, C	6	5, 8, 10	CC		

Abbreviations in Table: B – BFRP, C – CFRP, G-GFRP, CC-Conventional Concrete, EC-eco concrete, HSC-high strength concrete, HVFAC-high volume fly ash concrete, FAC-fly ash concrete, RAC-recycled aggregate concrete, UHPFRC-ultra high performance fiber reinforced concrete, X=yes.

Notes: ¹Nominal US FRP bar sizes have been rounded to the closest mm, so #3 (10mm), #4 (13mm), #5 (16mm), #6 (19 mm).

ESTIMATION OF BAR STRESS AND MAXIMUM DEVELOPABLE BAR STRESS

In the pull-out test, the stress distribution is not constant along the embedment length. Hence, an average bond stress is defined as:

$$\tau = \frac{P}{\pi d_b l_b} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where P is the tensile load, d_b is the rebar diameter, and l_b is the embedment length. The relationship between the bond stress defined by Eq. (1) and the slip between the rebar and the

concrete is used to analyse the bond behaviour (Baena et al. 2009). The reinforcing surface also plays an important role in the bond strength. If greater frictional resistance is developed between the rebar and the concrete, bond strength will increase. Similarly, if the bar surface treatment allows for mechanical bearing, bond strength can be improved further. ACI 440.1R-15 presents Eq. 2 for developable bar stress.

$$f_{fe} = \frac{\sqrt{f'_c}}{\alpha} \left(13.6 \frac{l_e}{d_b} + \frac{c}{d_b} \frac{l_e}{d_b} + 340 \right) \leq f_{fu} \quad (\text{ACI 440.1R-15 Eq. 10.1c}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

ACI 440.1R-15 states that embedment lengths shorter than $20d_b$ are not recommended and that additional work needs to be performed to determine the effect of the chosen factor of safety for bond on the flexural reliability of the specimen. When applying Eq. 2 for design purposes, ACI 440.1R-15 states it should be assumed that the maximum achievable bar stress varies linearly from 0 to the value produced by Eq. 2 (ACI 440.1R-15 Eq. 10.1c) along the first $20d_b$ of the bar embedment. Based on published durability bond related work, conditioning of bond specimens due to environment such as high temperature, alkaline environment, sustained stress, moisture, etc. have been shown to reduce bond performance. The scope of this study does NOT consider degradation in bond due environment or physical conditioning and only considered test data from specimens tested under a laboratory-controlled condition without any preconditioning, but literature including some published works in Table 1 have examined various types of conditioning and their effects on bond. It should also be noted, that in the calculation of f_{fe} , the ACI 440.1R environmental reduction factor, C_e , for the bars was applied within the analysis.

ANALYSIS AND COMPARISON OF THE DATABASE

Since the FRP bar properties including bar diameter, cross sectional area, tensile capacity, modulus of elasticity, etc. all vary by manufacturer as well as the concrete strength/properties used in the database, an approach was undertaken to view the pull-out results from the database through the perspective of upper and lower bandwidths as the maximum developable bar stress based on Eq. 2 (ACI 440.1R-15 Eq. 10.1c) was considered. Table 2 reports the upper and lower regions used to compare the data set to. These values were selected from the experimental research data collected from the aforementioned publications and align with the variation of the study properties. The scope of this paper will focus on the GFRP data that was assembled only, while future work will examine the other bar types.

Table 2: Limits of lower and upper bandwidth to compare Eq. 2 and dataset

GFRP reinforcing bar size	Bar area (in ²)	Concrete strength (psi)	Bar tension f_{fu}^* (ksi)
#3	0.28-0.40	4000-8000	100-150
#4	0.50-0.54	4000-8000	100-150
#5	0.63-0.68	4000-8000	100-150
#6	0.75-0.84	4000-8000	80-100

Table note: f_{fu}^* is the guaranteed tensile strength before applying C_e factor per ACI 440.1R-15.

Distribution of Data Collected

Envelopes for ACI 440.1R-15 Eq. 10.1c may be developed to determine the maximum developable stress in the bar for given criteria considering the $20d_b$ linear adjustment to zero. For example, if the concrete strength varies from 4000 psi to 8000 psi using the prior case study mentioned above or the bar diameter varies (and thereby bar area), Fig. 6 results illustrate how variables affect the maximum developable stress in the bar for given criterion. Increasing the concrete strength will improve the bond strength capacity as shown in Fig. 6. It may also be noted that as bar area increases, the maximum developable stress in the bar is reduced. This is related to the surface area to volume (SA/V) ratio of the bar or contact area (i.e., bonded surface area) of the bar relative to the cross-sectional bar area. Even though the bar area may increase,

due to the contact area with the concrete, the bond stress is more limited. While these envelopes were plotted to an embedment length of 12 inches, this investigation was more interested in short embedment lengths with much of the collected test data being 6 inches or less which is more aligned with actual field scenarios for short bar embedment including repair where embedment access is limited.

Figure 6. Maximum developable bar stress with varying f'_c (left) and bar size d_b (right)

Data fit to ACI 440.1R-15 Equation 10.1c

In this paper the GFRP data was collected and compared to the current ACI 440.1R Eq.10.1c. This paper does not attempt to suggest any refinements or calibration factors at this stage of the analysis, but merely examines the data to investigate the level of conservatism relative to the data collected. It should be noted that the $0.7 C_c$ factor has been applied to Eq. 2 (Eq.10.1c) reducing f_{fe}^* to f_{fe} as prescribed in ACI 440.1R. This considers any environmental reductions that may occur due to degradation in a field application. The results of the data collected is presented in Fig. 6.

Figure 7. GFRP peak bar stress developed from experimental data relative to ACI 440 Eq. 10.1c

Discussion of Results

In this paper the GFRP bars evaluated included multiple manufactures and different bar properties as reported in the cited publications. They were then grouped within the #3 to #6 rebar size categories as shown in Fig. 7 and then compared to a lower and upper envelop based on the variation of the

material geometry and properties. In terms of the scatter of data, this is anticipated as properties within the studies varied including the manufacturer where fibre-resin distributions varied along with bar sizes/properties. Based upon the data collected, the #3 GFRP data set Eq. 2 appears quite conservative. The same can be said for #4 and #5 GFRP dataset. This is irrespective of the type of concrete or variation in concrete/bar properties. In the case of #6 bars, some of the test results yielded results closer to the upper bound limits. However, even these results were quite conservative because as illustrated in Fig. 7d, the concrete used had a lower strength and may be benchmarked closely to the lower bound curve limit. The results show that for even some specialty concrete like HVFAC, the developable maximum stress limits appear conservative. While this particular study is not recommending if any modifications should be introduced at this time, it does highlight that for a variety of bar surface treatments, bar sizes, bar properties, short embedment lengths, in different types of concretes, the current ACI 440.1R approach appears quite conservative even for the newer generation of bars that included more recent test results and several specialty concretes.

CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

The following concluding observations from this analysis are presented:

- Within the range of properties and variables collected within the database, the variation in the upper and lower limits from ACI 440.1R-15 Eq. 10.1c are rather modest for the smaller bar diameters.
- A large portion of the data within the dataset actually developed much higher peak bar stresses than limited to by current ACI 440.1R guidelines. While research studies show degradation in bond performance, it may be noted that the 0.7 C_c factor was considered in this analysis.
- Current ACI 440.1R maximum developable bar stress limits appear conservative for the database collected within this study. More investigation is warranted to examine if any adjustments or calibration factors are warranted for different grades or type of concrete that utilize GFRP bars to make more economic use of the FRP materials.
- More work needs to be undertaken to fully understand the bond behavior of adhesively anchored embedded GFRP bars and their long-term durability behavior since this study indicated it may be a prominent failure mode in pull-out when used in field applications to bond GFRP bars. While some studies have been undertaken, more data on a larger set of variables is still needed in the author's opinion. Guidelines in ACI 440 are recommended to be developed to aid practitioners using FRP bars in adhesively bonded dowel applications.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is found in its entirety in the referenced technical publications.